

THE USE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY WITH THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE PRINCIPLE OF INDIVIDUALIZATION IN ENGLISH LESSONS

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ANNOTATION: At the present stage, new requirements are imposed on the professional competence of teachers and teachers of the Russian language - having competence in the use of information technology, in teaching the Russian language and culture [1]. However, an analysis of the experience of using information technologies in the educational process shows that for many teachers, the use of new computer technologies often comes down to the transfer of traditional classroom forms of work to teaching a language through computer programs. This article studies the issue which would significantly enrich the linguistic and cultural practice of students, as well as develop their skills in independent learning activities.

KEYWORDS: speed, maneuverability, efficiency, ability to view, multimedia functions.

INTRODUCTION

It should be noted that the use of information technology greatly helps in the work of a teacher. Today, information technologies are used in almost every lesson. As an example, let us cite the words of Shutova Oksana Georgievna, a teacher, who says: "The use of computer technologies is not the influence of fashion, but a necessity dictated by the current level of development of education. The advantages of using ICT can be reduced to two groups: technical and didactic [3]. Technical advantages are speed, maneuverability, efficiency, the ability to view and listen to fragments and other multimedia functions. The didactic advantages of interactive lessons are the creation of an effect of presence ("I saw it!"), Students develop a sense of authenticity, the reality of events, interest, a desire to learn and see more" .

METHODS

The use of ICT in the work practice of Shutova O.G. carried out in the following areas:

1. Creating presentations for lessons.
2. Working with Internet resources.
3. Use of ready-made training programs.
4. Development and use of your own proprietary programs.

The following tasks are solved with the help of computer technologies:

- increasing the intensity of the lesson;
- increasing student motivation;
- monitoring their achievements.

Boris Vladimirovich Egorov in his article "Use of a computer in the professional activities of a teacher" says that there are many reasons for the computerization of physics teaching. A person who has mastered a personal computer (PC) quickly becomes convinced that with its help one can write, draw, draw and do many other things more productively than without it [10]. Typing on a computer and printing a test assignment is much faster and more convenient than writing them by hand or typing them on a typewriter. Once entered into the computer's memory, they can be printed, and if necessary, the content of the tasks can be easily adjusted. A computer with Internet access can help a teacher and student obtain a variety of useful additional information.

RESULTS

Having studied and summarized the experience of teachers, he identified the following ways of using computer technology in the classroom [6]:

- preparation of printed handouts (tests, independent work, flashcards for individual work);
- multimedia support for explaining new material (presentations, audio recordings of real lectures, educational videos, computer models of physical experiments);
- interactive training in an individual mode;

- conducting computer laboratory work;
- processing experimental data by students (constructing tables, graphs, creating reports);
- monitoring the level of knowledge using test tasks;
- use of Internet resources in lessons and in preparation for them [7].

DISCUSSION

Svetlana Vladimirovna Andreeva, Russian teacher, says: "I teach Russian at the gymnasium on the basis of modern educational technologies: collaborative learning, part of which is the project method, problem-based learning, including search and research methods, new information and communication technologies, interactive technologies teaching [11]. These technologies fit most organically into the framework of communicative, student-oriented, individual, differentiated, activity-based approaches to teaching the Russian language. These technologies are directly aimed at the formation and implementation of the principle of individuality.

The use of ICT tools in my lessons can be divided into several groups [8]:

- use of educational and educational programs on CDs;
- creating and using your own electronic educational resources (presentations) in the classroom;
- use of presentations created by students independently or with the help of a teacher or parents;
- use of Internet resources."

CONCLUSION

Thus, we can conclude that many practicing teachers today actively use information technology in the teaching process. Practice shows that the use of ICT helps teachers solve many pedagogical problems [9].

Undoubtedly, information technology serves as a means of implementing the principle of individualization. ICT allows the teacher to select individual tasks for students with different levels of preparation. And the students themselves can work on the rock at the pace they personally need. And ICT does not stop there, but continues to develop and be introduced into the educational process.

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